

Behavioural Deviance and Perceived Parenting Style- A Study of North Kashmir

Waseem Raja¹ Dr. Aamina Parveen²

¹ Ph.D. research scholar, Dept. of Education, University of Kashmir

² Assistant Professor, Dept. of Education, University of Kashmir

Abstract:- The main purpose of this study was to determine the prevalence of behavioural deviance and perceived parenting styles among higher secondary school students. Descriptive survey was employed as the design. The sampling procedure adopted by the investigator was random sampling (Simple). 403 Higher secondary school students of district Baramullah comprise the sample of the study. Parenting Style Scale by Gupta & Mehtani (2017) and Behaviour Deviance Scale by Chauhan and Aurora (1989) were utilized to collect the data. The collected data was analysed with the use of percentage and frequency counts. It was inferred from the analysis that behavioural deviance is prevalent among 16.27 % of adolescent students. The results also indicate that permissive parenting style is associated with the highest portion of school-going adolescents who engage in anti-social behaviours, followed by autocratic, uninvolved, and democratic parenting styles. Moreover, the results also reveal that most of the students were raised with democratic parenting style followed by autocratic, uninvolved and permissive parenting style.

Keywords:- Behavioural Deviance, Perceive Parenting Style and Prevalence.

I. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is characterized by an extreme upheaval in both behavioural and emotional domains. It is a period between 10-19 years of age as stated by WHO (Rutter et al., 1976). The adolescents have a hard time figuring out how to develop their own identity while still adhering to social rules (Steinberg, 1987). They have been exposed to social changes as a result of rapid urbanization and modernization. Moreover, the resulting disintegration of family structure, inadequate or excessive parental supervision and confusion make the school-going adolescents more prone to maladaptive thoughts and deviant behaviour (Sadock, 2000). Behavioural deviance refers to any behaviour or action that goes against the norms or laws of a society (Bolu-steve & Esere, 2017). It has been defined as a behaviour that deviates from acceptable standards of a particular educational institution (Peretomode, 2011). It is a denial of the ideals and values of an institution or a group, as well as rejection of school rules and regulations. Societies have diverse definitions of what constitutes behavioural deviance. As a result, a behaviour that is deemed normal in one society may be regarded as deviant in another. The incidences of deviant behaviour can be found to be on increase in every part of the society; it is especially important to pay attention about the teenagers who are in the higher secondary schools. The

reasons for this are that such adolescents are in critical times of their lives, during which the basis for the development of information, attitudes, skills, personalities and other key attributes are being set. Deviant behaviours among adolescent school-going students have been on the rise in recent years across the world. A number of deviant behaviours have been observed among school-going teenagers, including theft, bullying, fighting, examination malpractice, truancy, smoking and drug abuse (Esere, 2008). These deviant behaviours among adolescents are not just exclusive to developed countries, but they are equally prevalent in developing countries (Asiyai, 2019 & Adegun, 2013). Various research studies have demonstrated that a variety of factors such as low socioeconomic status, poor academic performance, student-teacher relationships, poor neighbourhood and social media foster the development of deviant behaviour in adolescent students (Jude & Margaret, 2018; Sonali, 2017; Ayorinde, & Adegboyega, 2017; Mideva, Emily, & David 2016; Cheng, 2001). In addition to these listed factors, one of the most significant contributors to the emergence of anti-social behaviour is parenting style (Hoeve et al., 2008).

Parenting style may be described as a system or set of behaviours that characterize the parent-child interactions throughout a wide variety of sittings and helps them to have a good relationship. Parenting style deals with how parents treat their child's material and psychological needs and what parents from their child. It is an effective and determining element that plays an essential part in a child's growth and development (Eriega, 2014). It is Diana Baumrind's foundational collection of research studies in which she observed parents' interaction with their children to obtain knowledge about child-raising (Baumrind, 1971 & 1967). The results of Baumrind led to the conception of four parenting styles, which are as follows: 1) **Democratic parenting style** is characterized by a high level of control and warmth as well as a willingness to provide autonomy. Such parents urge their children to be self-sufficient and maintain control and limits on their behaviour. The child's point of view is taken into consideration when making decisions, but the parent retains the ultimate responsibility. 2) **Autocratic parents** show high control, less affection, and less autonomy towards their children. Such parents use a harsh approach to discipline and expect their children to obey the instructions. These parents appear to be cold and uncaring, do not participate their children in decision making and place a high restriction on autonomous behaviour. 3) **Permissive parenting style** is one where there is a lot of warmth but not as much control. Instead of giving children autonomy, such parents let them make decisions for themselves even when

they cannot. In their parenting, they are passive and lenient, and feel that the best way to display their love is to fulfill the demands of children without knowing the consequences. 4) **Uninvolved parenting style** is characterized by a lack of warmth, limited control, and a lack of concern for offering liberty. These parents may be able to react to the needs of children for easily accessible materials, but they are lacking in parenting skills which include interaction, discipline, control, guidance and expression of love and care. Such parents are careless about their parenting, being too preoccupied with their own problems to devote time and energy to their children's wellbeing.

The problem of behavioural deviance among teenage students is becoming a growing concern for teachers, parents, law enforcement officers, and members of society (Jacob & Adegboyega, 2017). If these anti-social problems are not addressed at an early intervention, they could lead to more violent types of behaviours like terrorism and other criminal activities in the community at large (Aute et al., 2020). Numerous studies have discovered a link between the quality of parenting style and the occurrence of behavioural deviance in their children (Stevens et al., 2007; Mulvaney & Mebert, 2007; Aunola & Kurmi, 2005). Many studies on deviant behavior have been done at the national and international levels. However, the prevalence of behavioural deviance and perceived parenting styles has not been studied in the Kashmir valley yet. There is a lot of work in this study because the researcher wants to determine the prevalence of behavioural deviance and different types of perceived parenting styles among adolescent students.

A. Objectives of the study

- To study behavioural deviance among senior secondary school students.
- To study parenting styles among senior secondary school students.
- To study behavioural deviance of senior secondary school students with different parenting styles (Democratic, Autocratic, Permissive and Uninvolved).

B. Research Questions

- What is the prevalence of behavioural deviance among senior secondary school students in district Baramullah?
- What is the percentage of perceived parenting styles among senior secondary school students in district Baramullah?
- What is the prevalence of behavioural deviance among senior secondary school students with different parenting styles (Democratic, Autocratic, Permissive and Uninvolved) in district Baramullah?

C. The Sample

The current study's target population consists of 11th and 12th grade students enrolled in various government higher secondary schools within the district of Baramullah. A sample of 403 students was drawn from different higher secondary schools using a simple random sampling technique.

D. Instruments Used

Chauhan and Aurora's (1989) "Behaviour Deviance Scale" was utilized to determine the prevalence of behavioural deviance. Specifically, this scale comprises of thirty items separated into three dimensions: W.D. (Withdrawing Deviance), E.E.D. (Expectation Evasion Deviance) and R.D. (Rebellion Deviance). According to the scale norms, the respondents who receive t-60 or above score in any of the three dimensions stated above are classified as behaviourally deviant. In contrast, respondents who receive a t-60 below score are classified as non-deviants.

Gupta and Mehtani's (2017) "Parenting Style Scale" was used to estimate the percentage of perceived parenting styles. This scale comprises of forty-four items that are distributed into four types of parenting styles such as Democratic, Autocratic, Permissive and Uninvolved. According to the scale norms, the respondents who achieve the highest score in any of these four parenting styles are deemed to be the most dominant parenting style.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The primary objective of this research study was to assess the prevalence of behavioural deviance and perceived parenting styles among senior secondary school students. According to the data in **table 1**, a significant portion of senior secondary school students (SSSS) in district Baramullah engage in behavioural deviance. Out of four hundred three students, sixty-six showed behavioural deviance, representing **16.27 %** of all participants; while as out of four hundred three students, three hundred thirty-seven are non-deviants, representing 83.63 %. Our findings are in line with Fatoki (2012), who found that behavioural deviance was present in 12.60 % secondary school students in Nigeria. The reported results are in accordance with the study conducted by Sarkhel, Sinah, Aurora and DeSarkar (2006), who found that about 27 percent students display anti-social behaviours in Kanke. Another research study by Revappala, Bhatathi and Dowda revealed that 10.43% of adolescent students in Karnataka engaged in deviant behaviours.

The data in the **table 2** shows the percentage of various perceived parenting styles among SSSS in district Baramullah. Out of four hundred three students, two hundred ninety-five were raised under democratic parenting style, which accounts for 73.20 %; eighty-two students raised under autocratic parenting style which accounts for 20.35 %; eleven students raised under permissive parenting style, which accounts for 2.73 %; and fifteen students raised under uninvolved parenting style, which accounts for 3.72 %. Additionally, the findings reveal that majority of the students were raised in a democratic parenting style followed by autocratic, uninvolved and permissive parenting styles. Kiran, Farooqi & Ahmed (2019) concurred with the findings of this study and reported that democratic parenting style was the most prevalent among secondary school children in Shiwal Division, followed by autocratic and permissive parenting styles. This study also corroborates with the work of Efobi and Nwokolo (2014), who concluded that the most common parenting style used by the parents in Nigeria was

democratic parenting style, followed closely by autocratic then uninvolved and permissive parenting style, which was found to be the least often utilized parenting style. The study conducted by Akin (2012) is also in line with this study who found that democratic parenting style among Muslim adolescent students.

Table 3, display the prevalence of behavioural deviance among SSSS with different types of parenting styles in district Baramullah. The details in the said table show that out of two hundred ninety-five students who have democratic parents, four are behaviourally deviant, representing 1.35 percent. Out of eighty-two students who have autocratic parents, fifty-one are behaviourally deviant, representing 62.19 percent. Out of eleven students who have permissive parents, seven are behaviourally deviant, representing 63.63 percent and out of fifteen students who have uninvolved parents, five are behaviourally deviant, representing 33.33 percent. Results also reveal that the permissive parenting style has the highest percentage of students which display

deviant behaviour followed by autocratic, uninvolved and democratic parenting styles. The obtained results are in line Miller, Diorio and Dudley (2002) who revealed that children who were raised by permissive parenting style had a greater indigence of engagement in deviant behaviours such as misbehavior in school premises, cigarette smoking, fights, alcohol and drug use, theft, impulsiveness and emotional outbursts. The findings of Mutuku et al (2019) showed that approximately sixty-seven percent of school-going adolescents raised by autocratic parenting display behavioural deviance, sixty-two percent adolescents raised by uninvolved parenting display behavioural deviance. Another research study by Ruturi (2020) has revealed that teenage students with autocratic and permissive parenting style were more like to engage in deviant acts, whereas deviant behaviour reduces to a great extent when parents adopt democratic parenting style. Hoeve et al (2009) and Azimi, Vizari and Kashani (2012) concluded that uninvolved and authoritarian parenting style had a significant influence on behavioural deviance.

Table 1: Prevalence of behavioural deviance among senior secondary school students in district Baramullah.

District	Frequency	Deviance Range (Above T-60)	% age	Non-Deviance Range (Below T-60)	%age
Baramullah	403	66	16.37	337	83.63 %

Table 2: Percentage of different perceived parenting styles among senior secondary school students in district Baramullah.

District Baramullah		
Parenting Style	Frequency	% age
Democratic parenting style	295	73.20 %
Autocratic parenting style	82	20.35 %
Permissive parenting style	11	2.71 %
Uninvolved parenting style	15	3.72 %
Total	403	100 %

Table 3: Prevalence of behavioural deviance among senior secondary school students in district Baramullah with different types of parenting styles.

District Baramullah			
Parenting Style	Frequency	No. of students with Behavioural Deviance	% age
Democratic parenting style	295	04	1.35 %
Autocratic parenting style	82	51	62.19 %
Permissive parenting style	11	07	63.63 %
Uninvolved parenting style	15	5	33.33 %
Total	403	66	16.37 %

III. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it is evident that behavioural deviance is prevalent among a sufficient number of senior secondary school students. The results also indicate that permissive parenting style is associated with the highest portion of school-going adolescents who engage in anti-social behaviours, followed by autocratic, uninvolved, and democratic parenting styles. It is, therefore, necessary for the parents, school officials, and government to put in place appropriate measures to curb deviant acts.

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